

DAMAGE MONITORING OF FIBER-METAL LAMINATES USING OPTICAL FIBER SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

Optical fiber vibrations sensors(OFVSs) and extrinsic Fabry-Perot interferometer(EFPI) were used in damage monitoring of fiber-metal laminates(FML). The cantilevered section in the OFVS moves opposite direction to the rest of the sensor in response to an applied vibration, and the amount of light coupled between the two fibers is modulated. The FML was fabricated using carbon/epoxy prepreg and Al1050 sheets. Tensile and indentation tests were performed with the measurement of optical signal and acoustic emission(AE). The signals of the OFVS due to damages were quantitatively evaluated by wavelet transform(WT). In the indentation test, relative position and condition between the specimen and indenter were able to estimate by observing the fiber-optic interference fringes of EFPI. The macro-crack of FML was initiated by fiber breakage because plies in the FML prevent the crack growth and consolidation. The OFVS detected many damage signals caused by fiber breakages and delamination during the test. It was found that damage information of comparable in quality to acoustic emission data could be obtained from the optical fiber vibration sensor signals.

KEY WORDS: Smart Structures, Optical Fiber Sensor, Damage Monitoring, Fiber-Metal Laminate

INTRODUCTION

The increased use of composite materials in smart structures and industries has resulted in the need for new damage detection techniques. Composite materials are used in increasingly complex constructions, which may not be readily accessible using conventional techniques such as x-radiography, acoustic emission (AE) and ultrasonics. All these techniques have a common limitation in that continuous damage assessment cannot be made in situ during the service of structures. An important component of smart structures is the optical fiber sensor, which can detect strain levels, temperature and acoustic emission. Recently, based on the smart structure concept, optical fiber sensors have been increasingly applied to monitor various engineering and civil structural components. These fiber-optic smart structures allow engineers to add nervous systems to their designs, giving structures capabilities that would be difficult to achieve by other means.

Fiber-metal laminate (FML) is a new type of composite comprising stacking metal laminate and fiber prepreg. It is likely to become a principal material in aircraft construction because of its lightweight, high strength, fatigue resistance, and other properties. Compared with fiber-reinforced plastic, FML endures transverse loading well and has good impact properties. It also has a good plasticity and can accept metallic process and joining techniques such as milling, sawing, drilling, and riveting. The properties of FML can be selected by choosing the fiber prepreg (glass, graphite, aramid, etc.) and a metal laminate(Al, Fe, Cu, etc.), and by controlling the fiber orientation angle.

Several researchers [1-3] have designed and integrated optical fiber monitoring system for full-scale industrial constructions. Murphy et al.[4] gave results of full-scale static and fatigue testing of an F-15 aircraft using extrinsic Fabry-Perot interferometric(EFPI) sensors. Park et al.[5] used EFPI sensors to detect the onset of buckling and delamination growth in composite beams subjected to compressive loading. Vries et al.[6] reported the performance of EFPI sensors in a fatigue-loaded reinforced concrete specimen. Badcock and Fernando [7] designed and evaluated an intensity-based optical fiber sensor under fatigue loading conditions. Lee et al.[8] detected stiffness changes caused

by crack growth in a steel structure using an intensity-based optical fiber sensor. Kwon et al.[9] used an embedded Michelson interferometric fiber-optic sensor to detect matrix crack initiation of cross-ply composites during four-point bending tests. Tsuda et al.[10] investigated the interference signal response of a surface-mounted Michelson sensor to either dynamic or static loading. And Okabe et al.[11] applied fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors to detect transverse cracks in carbon fiber reinforced plastic laminates.

In recent years, considerable effort has been devoted to the development of optical fiber vibration sensors (OFVSs). This is because of the wide variety of applications in which it is necessary to monitor or accurately measure vibrations, which cannot be achieved by the traditional sensors based on piezoelectric or capacitive working principles. Doyle and Fernando [12] described a vibration monitoring system for detecting damage in a material using an intensity-based optical fiber vibration sensor. Several researchers have applied optical fiber vibration sensors in a fiber optic accelerometer [13], with emphasis on the low-frequency range and low-amplitude measurements. Yang and Han[14] introduced simple OFVS for locating impact points and detecting damage signal in CFRP.

In the present study, damage monitoring was demonstrated using OFVSs. The design, fabrication and operation of an inexpensive and simple intensity-based OFVS are described. Indentation and tensile tests were also performed by measuring optical and acoustic emission signals.

OPTICAL FIBER VIBRATION SENSOR

1. Sensor operation and construction

The intensity-based OFVSs used in this study consist of two optical fibers held in close proximity

to each other, and are based on the principle of intensity modulation. The amount of light captured by the second optical fiber depends on its acceptance angle, and the distance and radial offsets between the optical fibers. Fig. 1 shows the configuration of the OFVS. The cantilevered section moves opposite direction to the rest of the sensor in response to an applied vibration, and the amount of light coupled between the two fibers is modulated. We used single mode optical fibers (Samsung Co.) with a coating diameter of $250\mu\text{m}$ and a cladding diameter of $125\mu\text{m}$. The length of the fiber-optic cantilever can be varied according to the sensor application. Sensors with a shorter cantilever can respond to higher frequencies, but tend to be less sensitive than longer ones since they give a smaller change in intensity. For use as a low-frequency accelerometer, Morante et al [13] used an optical fiber cantilever about 20mm long. In this study, the cantilever was 5mm long for quick response and smaller size of the sensor. The coating of one optical fiber end was stripped to about 5mm and cleaved. The coating of the other fiber was stripped as short as possible ($<0.5\text{mm}$) and cleaved. The sensor was assembled by inserting the cleaved end of the fiber into the capillary tube with an inner diameter of about $253\mu\text{m}$, using a special xyz-positioning stage.

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the OFVS.

The core diameter of the single mode fiber is small ($9.3\mu\text{m}$), so that we employed single mode fibers in the OFVS to improve sensitivity. Other researchers [12, 13] have used multimode fibers with a much larger core diameter. By inserting the coated part of the optical fiber into the capillary tube, a simple OFVS can be manufactured without the additional fiber supporting guide needed in Doyle and Fernando's design [12]. The completed sensor was attached to the surface of a test specimen. Because the output signal of the OFVS is very weak for bending strains, the sensor was carefully attached so as not to bend during tests.

2. Characterization of the sensor

Changes in output of the OFVS are caused by a relative shift or offset of the two identical fibers. The three possible types of offset are radial, longitudinal, and angular. The longitudinal offset, i.e. gap separation in the OFVS, relates to the magnitude of the output signal and has little relation to vibration sensing. The angular offset between the core axes has a greater effect on changes in the signal. However, the angular offset is negligible since the deflection of the fiber tip is around several micrometers and the cantilever is very long compared to its diameter. Intensity modulation in the OFVS is mainly due to the radial shift of the fiber-optic cantilever. In the view of the core diameter of the fiber, the output signal of the OFVS changes mostly with up to about 10 μ m of radial offset at the fiber tip.

Fig. 2. Vibration characteristics of the OFVS.

Fig. 3. Variations of the first natural frequency of

the OFVS with the length of the fiber-optic cantilever.

$$f_1 = \frac{C_1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho AL^4}} \quad (1)$$

where C_1 is a geometrical factor, ρ is the density of the optical fiber, E is its Young's modulus, I is the second moment of inertia, A is cross-sectional area of the beam and L is its length. For the optical fibers used in this study, $\rho = 2340 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $E = 65 \text{ GPa}$ and $d = 125 \mu\text{m}$. The response of the OFVS can be adjusted by altering the length L of fiber-optic cantilever. Fig. 2 shows vibration characteristics of the OFVS. In the early stages of the response, the OFVS signal oscillates dramatically due to large-amplitude vibration of the internal fiber-optic cantilever. This vibration vanishes after about 15 msec. The first natural frequency of the sensor is 3970 Hz. The sensor resonance can be tuned by varying the length of the fiber-optic cantilever. Fig. 3 compares the calculated and measured first natural frequency of the OFVSs. The first natural frequency of the OFVS changes from 10^5 to 10^2 Hz when the length of the fiber-optic cantilever beam varies between 1 – 20 mm. The lengths of the beam in three sensors used are 4.725, 5.150 and 5.625 mm respectively. Good agreement is observed between measurement and the calculation based on equation (1).

EXPERIMENT

The OFVS and EFPI were illuminated by a 1.5 mW 1310 nm laser diode. The laser beam was launched into a 2 X 2 bidirectional coupler that splits the optical signals. The split light was fed into each sensor and the transmitted and reflected light signals were detected using InGaAs photodiodes. The fiber optic signals received by the photodiode were transmitted to a PC. Manufactured optical fiber sensors were attached to the surface of the specimens. Aluminum laminate (Al1050) and carbon/epoxy prepreg (USN124 type A, SK chemical Co.) were used as a base material for FML. Aluminum laminate was surface treated to increase bonding strength between aluminum laminate and fiber prepreg. Surface treated aluminum laminate was stacked with fiber prepreg, then cured using hot press. Fabricated FML consists of three plies aluminum laminates and four ply fiber

prepregs.

For damage monitoring, we performed indentation testing and tensile testing. Specimens were loaded by UTM (Universal Testing Machine, Shimadzu Co.). The stacking sequence chosen for the indentation test was [Al/15/-15/Al/-15/15/Al] noted as FML[15/-15]. The dimensions of the specimen were $100 \times 100 \text{mm}^2$, and four sides were clamped. The indenter was of a hemispherical shape with a diameter of 12.7mm. The indentation test was performed at a crosshead speed of 3mm/min. The OFVS and EFPI were attached to the surface at 30mm and 35mm from a clamped end of the composite specimen respectively. Because the output signal of the OFVS is very weak for bending strain, the sensor was carefully attached so as not to bend. One channel AE measurement was simultaneously performed to evaluate the damage process during the test. A resonant type AE sensor (R15, PAC) was attached on the specimen. The AE signals passed through a preamplifier with a gain of 40dB were recorded in an AE analyzer (SPARTAN-AT, PAC). The threshold value of AE measurement was set at 45dB.

Fig. 4 Load-deflection curve and (a)AE amplitude, (b)AE count rate during indentation test

The stacking sequence for the tensile test was [Al/0/0/Al/0/0/Al]. The dimensions of the specimen were $250 \times 25 \text{mm}^2$. The OFVS, EFPI and the AE sensor were attached to the specimen, and a resistive strain gauge was also attached to the surface of the specimen near the optical fiber sensor. To prevent tensile strains at the OFVS, the OFVS was attached perpendicular to the loading direction. The loading speed was 3mm/min. Load, strain, and the fiber-optic output signals were recorded using PC-LabCard and data acquisition software. During the indentation and tensile tests, the sampling rate of the fiber-optic signal was 1000 samples/sec.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Indentation test

Damage detection in composite materials has been extensively studied using optical fiber sensors, including EFPI and Michelson sensors. The output signal of these interferometric sensors has a sinusoidal form as a result of the static strain. For the same extent of rapid dynamic small deformations due to fiber failure in composites, the failure signals in the fiber-optic signal can give rise to different amplitudes as a result of nonlinearity in the sinusoidal-intensity vs. phase curve of the sensor output [9].

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

(c)

(c)

Fig. 5 Load-deflection curve and (a) OFVS signal, (b) AE count, (c) WT of OFVS signal during indentation test(3.6-4.6mm).

Fig. 6 Load-deflection curve and (a) OFVS signal, (b) AE count, (c) WT of OFVS signal during indentation test(4.6-5.6mm).

The sensitivity of the interferometric sensor therefore varies with the output phase in damage detection signals. This is an intrinsic feature of such sensors, so that the failure signals of composites occasionally cannot be found from the fiber optic signal. The OFVS detects the damage and failure signals in the composites as a short vibration of duration several milliseconds. On the test time scale, the damage signal of the OFVS therefore appears as a pulse. This is similar in shape to the AE count signals measured by the AE analyzer. In this study, wavelet transform(WT) is introduced in order to more accurately evaluate the signal of OFVS when the breakage of reinforced fibers occurs and delamination grows. WT is capable of revealing aspects of data that other signal analysis techniques miss, such as trends, breakdown points, discontinuities in higher derivatives and self-similarity. In this study, MATLAB toolbox[®] was used to process the signal of the OFVS. The used analyzing function was Daubechey function 4(Db4) and decomposition was performed one time. After the WT, de-noising was performed to remove the noise level signal.

Fig. 4 shows the load-deflection curve and AE amplitude during the indentation test. AE signals with an amplitude greater than 100dB are marked at 100dB owing to the limitation of the AE analyzer. Fig. 5 and 6 represents the load-deflection curve, fiber-optic signals, AE count rate and WT of the OFVS signal during the indentation test. Before deflection of 4mm, a small number of AE count rate were recorded, and most AE signals had an amplitude under 80dB. The load-deflection curve shows a closely linear relationship before 4mm. Damage in the specimen at this stage must be small scale, such as matrix cracking. As the indenter moved forward, many AE signals with larger

amplitude including 100dB were recorded. The load-deflection curve shows some discontinuities at several points due to fiber breakages in the specimen. AE signals with an amplitude of 100dB were also detected at those same points. Larger damage compared with the previous stage occurs and some reinforcing fibers break in the specimen at this stage. After deflection of 5.2mm, most of reinforcing fibers in the specimen broke, and the indenter penetrated the specimen. As the indenter moved through the specimen, many AE signals were detected.

Fig. 7 Load-displacement curve and (a)AE amplitude, (b)AE count rate during tensile test.

The OFVS signals were almost uniform in the early stage of the test, and showed a similar trend to the AE count signal. The magnitude of the OFVS output signal is not necessarily proportional to the AE count rate. This is because the fiber-optic cantilever may move in a circular fashion rather than just ‘up and down’ when the OFVS is subjected to arbitrary impact. Fig. 5 shows the fiber-optic signals and the AE count rate along with WT of the OFVS signal for the deflection of 3.6-4.6mm. The load curve shows a discontinuity and AE count signal with large amplitude is detected at 4.44mm. The OFVS also detected the damage at the same point. The EFPI detected large-scale damages at 4.8, 4.9, 5 and 5.2mm that could be also shown in the load-deflection curve. However EFPI could not detect damage events at other points. It requires special data processing techniques and suitable experimental setup. As shown in Fig. 5(c), WT of the OFVS signal shows similar trend compared with the AE data. In Fig. 6, many significant peaks appeared in WT of the OFVS signal between 4.8-5.2mm. These peaks show good agreement with damage events where a high AE count rate was recorded.

2. Tensile test

Fig. 7 represents the load-displacement curve and AE amplitude during the tensile test. The strain gauge attached to the specimen deteriorated at about 1.1% strain. The load-displacement curve shows almost linear relationship during the test. Fig. 8 and 9 shows the load-displacement curve, fiber-optic signal, AE count rate and WT of the OFVS signal during the tensile test. Total amount of the AE count rate in the tensile test was small compared with the indentation test. This is because the tensile specimen consisted of 0 degree plies so that fiber breakage is the major damage in the specimen.

(a)

Fig. 8 Load-displacement curve and (a) OFS signal, (b) AE count, (c) WT of OFVS signal during tensile test(4.6-6.0mm).

Fig. 9 Load-displacement curve and (a) OFS signal, (b) AE count, (c) WT of OFVS signal during tensile test(6.0mm-end of test).

As shown in Fig. 7, AE amplitude increased according to the load increased. This is the typical behavior of the unidirectional composites. Before the displacement of 5mm, most AE signals had an amplitude under 80dB. After that point, major damage occurred in the tensile specimen due to fiber breakages within it. AE signals with an amplitude of 100dB were also detected at this stage. The trend of the AE signals was similar to the indentation test. The sudden discontinuity in the load-displacement curve at 5.7mm was caused by breakage of the large amount of fibers in the specimen. In Fig. 8 and 9, WT of the OFVS signal shows good agreement with the damage events detected by the commercial AE analyzer. Because the major damage mechanism in the tensile specimen is fiber breakage, the OFVS detects the failure signal more accurately than the indentation test.

CONCLUSIONS

Intensity-based OFVSs have been constructed and used for damage monitoring of FML. By using a bare fiber-optic cantilever beam, a simple OFVS can be constructed. It was found that damage information comparable in quality to acoustic emission data could be obtained from the OFVS signals. The OFVS proved to be effective for monitoring the damage process of the material studied here. The OFVS is very sensitive to damage signals in the composites, but has the disadvantages of weakness under bending strain and difficulty in measuring the absolute magnitude of vibrations. Despite these limitations, the characteristic advantages of the OFVS have been confirmed; in particular, the intensity-based OFVS system is easily built with inexpensive components, and does not require complex data processing routines such as fringe counting or an expensive high performance data acquisition system.

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